

MECHANISMS OF APPLYING THE CULTURAL SCIENCE APPROACH TO THE DIDACTIC PROCESS BASED ON THE INTEGRATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SUBJECTS

Safarova Rokhat Gaybullaevna

Doctor of Pedagogical sciences, Professor

Head department "Pedagogy and psychology of continuous education" Scientific Research
Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyoz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8397025>

Abstract. *In this article, in the process of higher pedagogical education, on the basis of the approach of cultural studies, the formation of social and cultural competence in future teachers, their preparation for the organization of gender relations, the integration of pedagogic subjects in order to successfully form social and cultural competence, the development of laws and regulations for the implementation of integration, the understanding of the cultural image of the world in order to effectively form the cultural outlook of teachers, the possibility of integrating the content of educational programs and educational modules was discussed. The article serves as an important resource for the scientific-pedagogical community, professors, future teachers, and researchers.*

Keywords: *cultural studies approach, socio-cultural competence, gender approach, pedagogical process, pedagogic subjects, integrative approach, professional competence, educational materials, educational modules, programs, educational topics, cognitive tasks, pragmatic tasks, active-technological tasks, negative and positive factors, creativity, stereotypes, models, concepts.*

Yesterday, 100 goals were set within the framework of the five important directions specified in the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoev dated 11.09.2023 No. PD-158. Most of these goals are characterized by the fact that they are oriented towards the comprehensive development of the continuous education system. For example, by developing the process of higher pedagogical education, it is necessary to give priority to the approach of cultural studies in the modernization of all links of the continuous education system. This, in turn, implies the improvement of the content of pedagogical education based on the approach of cultural studies.

Higher pedagogical education consists of an educational process organized on the basis of innovative approaches to the training of future teachers. The process of training future teachers covers two main directions: it incorporates educational actions in the directions of encouraging pedagogical and cultural-educational maturity. In the implementation of the educational process in these directions, solutions to a number of pedagogical tasks are sought. The solution of these tasks allows to determine the directions of individual development of future teachers, to determine the extent of cultural development. Within the framework of philosophical-pedagogical and cultural studies approaches, a cultured person appears as an independent, humane, spiritual, ready to perform practical activities, leading specialist in educating the young generation in the spirit of values.

From the time when a person takes the first steps in the educational process, he begins to acquire the skills of mastering socio-cultural values, understanding, performing many social roles, and feeling his gender belonging. In this process, teachers apply a gender approach to their education. According to H.Tojiboeva, M. Tilavova, N.M.Medvetskaya, L.V.Kolomiychenko's research, in the process of educating students based on the gender approach, they are taught knowledge of gender differences and similarities, the specificity of gender roles, the necessary information about their pedagogical and psychological interpretations, cultural-historical views, and national traditions. As a result, they perceive themselves as a person belonging to a certain gender, adopt the functions and moral stereotypes specific to it. At the same time, they learn the mechanisms of communication and interaction with others within the framework of behavioral norms based on their gender. In particular, there is a growing need to present the socially relevant norms of gender culture to students. According to this, gender culture embodies the points of view, principles, implementation of matrices, factors that shape social and cultural directions of gender, including gender roles, gender stereotypes, and family and marriage laws.

According to S.Aboim, the types of gender culture affect the self-expression of a person and the implementation of his activities. At the same time, gender culture helps to form the future teacher's attitude towards the environment and professional activity. Within the framework of the competence approach, the problem of equipping future teachers with a modern gender approach and gender culture is waiting for its solution in the current situation, where it is required to coordinate the educational process with the future specialist's worldview and current situation. Because today, the need to educate young people of a certain gender on the basis of gender is increasing, because the students have not developed enough skills to understand their gender, move within the framework of gender culture, and perform gender roles from the perspective of cultural studies. In most cases, teachers also do not pay attention to inculcating the sense of gender culture and gender belonging in students in educational institutions. The formation of skills to follow the gender approach in the training of future teachers is neglected by experts.

The preparation of future teachers for the implementation of the gender approach, and the preparation of students for the formation of cultured individuals are gaining special relevance. This, first of all, requires the development of socio-cultural competence of the future teacher. Because socio-cultural competence is part of the professional competence of the future teacher. Socio-cultural competence has a personal social character. Socio-cultural competence, in turn, embodies gender culture, gender values, cultural communication based on dialogue between boys and girls, ability to perform gender roles, positive outlook, ability to solve personal problems in socio-cultural environment. A large number of specialists have included informational, motivational, technological, reflexive competences in the socio-cultural competence. (A.V.Khutorskoy, I.A.Zimnyaya). Within the framework of socio-cultural competence, it is possible to show three levels of situations related to the pedagogical influence of future teachers on students: critical, base and actual levels.

The specific description of socio-cultural competence formed in the process of pedagogical education, its structural structure, indicators, criteria, and diagnostic methods of determining the degree of formation of socio-cultural competences are manifested.

The composition of socio-cultural competence consists of informational, motivational, technological and reflexive components. Indicators: social and cultural knowledge, personal interests, national and universal values, actions, reflexive skills. The criteria include: the scale of

socio-cultural relations, its provenance, systematic nature, stability of needs, orientation of motives, independence, initiative, creativity, awareness, compatibility, based on forecasts. It is desirable to check and determine the level of formation of socio-cultural competences in future teachers using diagnostic methods. Such methods include: checking the formation of gender culture in future teachers with the help of questionnaires, determining gender, that is, masculinity and femininity, showing the level of formation of socio-cultural competences in students using the expert evaluation method.

Our analysis shows that the main component of socio-cultural competence formed in future teachers and the relationship between them is formed through historical-cultural knowledge, art examples and social reality systematically presented to students. There is a certain relationship between informative and reflexive competencies, and this relationship ensures mutual influence of the competencies. The development of socio-cultural competence in the framework of professional competences is of special importance due to the fact that it is devoted to the solution of a scientifically based current problem. Because this problem is related to the preparation of the future specialist for the socialization of students.

Enrichment of existing approaches to the development of professional competence of future teachers includes systematic and cultural studies approaches and socio-cultural and psychological knowledge, which are considered as its components. Pedagogical activity in this direction is carried out based on the approach of cultural studies.

It is known that educational programs and educational modules are of great importance in the complete organization of the educational process without defects. The programs determine the sequence of educational topics, the time spent on mastering them, and show forms of control. The selection of educational materials within the framework of an integrative approach allows students to concentrate their attention on one point and coordinate, as well as accelerates the development of socio-cultural competence in them. This, in turn, facilitates the process of monitoring students' knowledge and competencies. A cultural studies approach allows students to have a more complete picture of the world. Approaching from this point of view, humanization of the educational process within the cultural studies approach, development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers, and preparation for regulating gender relations between educational subjects based on socio-cultural values. A legitimate question arises: what mechanisms should be created to implement the approach of cultural studies and integration between the disciplines of pedagogy?

For this, it is recommended to create the following conditions:

- compliance of the research objects with the content of pedagogic subjects;
- coordination and provision of research methods implemented within the framework of integrative educational subjects;
- such as integration of pedagogic subjects, based on general didactic rules and concepts.

Adherence to the above-mentioned conditions allows successful integration of the subjects of the pedagogical category. In this process, inter-subject integration, integration between study blocks and study modules is carried out. In textbooks, the possibilities of using cognitive, heuristic, creative, pragmatic, active-technological assignments will expand based on the integration of educational materials.

Along with positive factors in the integration of educational subjects, there are also factors that have a negative impact on the pedagogical process. These factors allow determining the tactics of pedagogical integration in most cases.

Among the positive factors, first of all, it can be shown that the educational materials selected on the basis of pedagogical integration serve to ensure the intellectual development of students. This factor of pedagogical integration is not used enough in the process of traditional pedagogical education.

Among the negative factors, it can be shown that there is no possibility of mutual integration of all subjects included in the content of pedagogic subjects. In this place, some topics included in the content of pedagogical education can be filled and enriched on the basis of interpretation in connection with the landscape of the cultural world.

Another negative factor is explained by some parts of the method of describing the content of an integrative educational module, presenting it to students, especially the difficulty of achieving the goal of this model to be understandable, convenient and productive for future teachers.

Integrating the system of pedagogical knowledge occupies a key place in the structure of the educational module. At the same time, pedagogical knowledge becomes part of the future teacher's professional competence and helps them to imagine didactic processes as a whole. For this purpose, it is necessary to use the possibilities of integrating the contents of pedagogic subjects with the contents of other educational subjects in the socio-humanitarian direction, on this basis, to create a clear idea of cultural and spiritual processes in students, to form a positive worldview and gender affiliation in them, to educate the qualities of resistance against mass culture, cultural models and a favorable pedagogical environment is created for them to fully understand the concepts.

Enriching the composition of competencies that will enable effective pedagogical activity in future teachers at the expense of 21st century skills is of special socio-cultural and pedagogical importance. Because future teachers are entrusted with the task of preserving universal values of peace, valuing independence, protecting the health of students and creating a positive cultural environment around them, feeling gender equality and gender differences. Therefore, successful integration of pedagogic sciences with other social and humanitarian sciences, effective use of the approach of cultural studies in this process is one of the urgent issues facing the pedagogic science and waiting for its solution. In order to successfully solve this problem, it is required to expand the scope of research on cognitive pedagogy.

Future teachers will get acquainted with cultural pedagogical models of a completely new nature, based on the study of approaches to the development of pedagogical teachings, the contribution of the Uzbek people to the world civilization. There is a need to learn them, master them and turn them into a component of their professional activities. Future teachers will discover new cultural models for themselves and will be able to understand their essence, having a deep understanding of the difficulties faced by our thinking ancestors on the way to the realization of self-development discoveries, the actions they took to overcome them.

How to apply the approach of cultural studies in the process of teaching subjects of the pedagogy category is also attracting the attention of experts. It is becoming a socio-pedagogical necessity to develop and propose research directions for solving the problem. For this, professors, teachers, and researchers should work together to find effective research mechanisms. The approach of cultural studies is mainly applied to pedagogical processes through the content of educational subjects of an integrative character, where related topics intersect. In this process, a

future teacher who successfully acquires culturally intellectually developed professional competencies appears as the main result.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ўзбекистон – 2030” стратегияси” 11.09.2023 йилдаги ПФ–158-сонли Фармони. <https://lex.uz/docs/6600413>
2. Safarova R. G. Developing professional competence of future professionals on the basis of cultural approach. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(9), 17–22.
3. Тожибоева Х.М. Гендер ёндашув асосида ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда “оммавий маданият”га қарши иммунитетни шакллантиришнинг педагогик стратегиялари: педагогика фанлари доктори дисс. – Т.: ТДПУ, 2022. – 222 б.
4. Тилавова М.М. Ўқувчиларда гендер тенглик ва фарқлар асосида умуммехнат кўникмаларини шакллантиришнинг педагогик асослари: Педагогика фанлари номзоди. ... дисс. – Т., 2008. – 130 б.
5. Зимняя И. А. Осваиваем социальные компетентности: учебное пособие / Российская академия образования, Московский психолого-социальный институт. – М.: Московского психолого-социального ин-та, 2011. – 591 с.
6. Коломийченко Л. В. Народная культура как средство формирования гендерной толерантности у детей старшего дошкольного возраста. – Пермь, 2013. – 115 с.
7. Медвецкая Н. М. Гендерные аспекты подготовки педагогов. Материалы Международного научно-практического семинара. - Витебск, 2010. - Ч. 2. - С. 172-175.
8. Хуторской А.В. Компетентностный подход в обучении. Научнометодическое пособие. – М.: Эйдос, 2013. – 73 с.
9. Aboim S. Gender cultures and the division of labour in contemporary Europe: a cross-national perspective // *Portuguese Journal of Social Science*. 2010. Vol. 58. № 2. P. 171-196.